

Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from a shipwreck found at Femern, Denmark

by

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Five samples from a shipwreck found at Femern vestlig landvinding were submitted for dendrochronological analysis, to determine their date and provenance. A single barrel stave was also submitted, so there are six samples in all. The results are described in this report.

Femern vestlig landvinding, Denmark

All the samples examined are of *Quercus sp.*, oak.

Four of the samples are dated. The results described here are grouped according to the structure from which they came (see fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Femern vestlig landvinding wreck, Denmark. The chronological position of the dated samples.

The wreck

Five samples are from timbers from the wreck structure. One of these, sample x10, was so eaten by shipworm that it was impossible to gain an uninterrupted series of tree-ring measurements, so this sample is not dated. Another sample, x1, contained only 90 tree-rings, and this could not be dated either.

The remaining three samples from the ship structure are dated. Sample x8 is from a ship plank, tangentially converted from the parent tree. It contains 114 tree-rings, all heartwood. Its tree-ring curve covers the period AD 1408-1521. Allowing for missing sapwood, the tree that this plank was made from was felled after AD 1529.

Sample x9 is from a framing timber from the ship. This sample appears tangentially converted from the parent tree. It contains 179 tree-rings, all heartwood, and covers the period AD 1362-1540. Allowing for missing sapwood again, the felling of the tree for this frame can be placed at after AD 1548.

Sample x11 is probably from the ship keel. It contains 122 tree-rings, all heartwood, and covers the period AD 1443-1564. Again, allowing for missing sapwood, the felling of this tree took place after AD 1572.

The outermost preserved tree-ring in the dated material from the ship structure is on the sample from the keel. The felling date estimate for this timber gives us a *terminus post quem* for the building of the ship, at **after AD 1572** (highlighted in blue in fig. 1).

The barrel stave

As mentioned above, a sample was also taken from a barrel stave found at the wreck site. This sample, x26, contains 125 tree-rings, only heartwood. It is radially converted from the parent tree. This sample covers the period AD 1493-1617. Allowing for missing sapwood, this sample is from a tree felled after AD 1628 (highlighted with pink in fig. 1).

The year 1644 is marked in fig. 1 with a red vertical line. This is the year of the historic sea battle of Fehmarn where the Danish fleet was defeated by the Swedes. The felling estimates of all the dated samples from the ship, and of the barrel stave, fall before this historic event, so the wreck could represent a ship that sank in this battle.

			Z2800039	Z280002a	Z280004a	Z2801019
Average Z280M001	frame x9	Z2800039	*	6.03	3.8	1.13
	keel? x11	Z280002a	6.03	*	5.62	0.13
	plank x8	Z280004a	3.8	5.62	*	0.51
	stave x26	Z2801019	1.13	0.13	0.51	*

Table 1. Femern vestlig landvinding wreck, Denmark. Result of the correlation (*t*-value) between the tree-ring curves from each dated sample with each other.

Provenance

The tree-ring curves from the dated samples match each other as shown in table 1. An average (Z280M001) of 203 years in length is built, which includes all three dated tree-ring curves from the ship structure. The correlation between this average and a range of tree-ring datasets for Northern Europe is shown in table 2. It is correlating best with chronologies for oak that derive from south Norway, including Norwegian timber that appears in Danish urban centres, and with diverse tree-ring datasets from south Scandinavian timber, exported to Scotland. The tree-ring curve from the barrel stave does not display significant correlation with the ship timbers and is dated separately (table 3). While the correlations are significant for the purposes of dating the object, it is not possible to suggest the provenance of the tree used for this barrel stave.

Filenames	-	-	Z280M001	
-	start	dates	AD1362	
-	dates	end	AD1564	
Chronologies for south Scandinavia				
Z1015M02	AD1305	AD1743	9.99	Copenhagen B&W Grund 24 trees (Daly 1997)
b&w+aalborg	AD1305	AD1771	8.98	B&W+Aalborg 5 timbers (Daly unpubl)
B027oak E pin	AD1315	AD1663	8.76	Gammel Strand Copenhagen oak pink 5 timbers (Daly 2016b)
B027oak F g...	AD1413	AD1689	7.58	Gammel Strand oak F green gr1 2 timbers (Daly 2016b)
H017M001	AD1434	AD1598	7.51	Aalborg Danmarksgræde A3 2 timbers (Daly 2018a)
B044M001	AD1349	AD1603	7.03	Favrholm Mølle II 7 timbers (Daly 2017)
8127M001	AD846	AD1771	6.47	Ålborg Østerå & Boulevarden 67 timbers (Daly 2000 2001)
WSwedM25	AD1344	AD1560	6.46	West Sweden 49 timbers (Daly unpubl)
2M000003	AD1460	AD1743	6.45	Copenhagen (Daly unpubl)
B027oak C o...	AD1331	AD1557	6.44	Gammel Strand Copenhagen C orange 23 timbers (Daly 2016b)
81M00004	AD1350	AD1480	6.39	kirker i Vendsyssel W Sweden group 24 timber (Daly 1998)
SM100001	AD1310	AD1539	6.25	Ystad area (Lund University)
B027oak F g...	AD1483	AD1690	6.23	Gammel Strand Copenhagen oak F green lt1 9 timbers (Daly 2016b)
H011M002	AD1386	AD1563	6.21	Aalborg Algade Tiendeladen hus 3 timbers (Daly 2016a)
SScanM25	AD1343	AD1548	6.18	Southern Scandinavia 36 timbers (Daly unpubl)
Chronologies from Scandinavian exports				
FTMAS2	AD1318	AD1572	12.53	Fenton Tower Scotland IMPORTS 5 timbers (Crone pers comm)
EDINCAS2	AD1358	AD1509	9.03	Edinburgh Castle IMPORTS 13 timbers (Crone pers comm)
QMBH01mn	AD1423	AD1550	8.44	Scotland Queen Mary's Bathhouse IMPORTS (Crone pers comm)
CARNCKx8	AD1317	AD1588	7.82	Carnock Castle Scotland IMPORTS (Crone pers comm)
DUNTARVI	AD1385	AD1529	7.51	Duntarvi Scotland IMPORTS 2 timbers (Crone pers comm)
jknoxh1	AD1466	AD1560	7.49	Knox Hall Scotland IMPORTS (Crone pers comm)
EP21505	AD1355	AD1505	7.47	Stirling Castle Scotland episode 2 (Crone pers comm)
StSerfM001	AD1377	AD1511	7.09	St Serfs church Dysart IMPORTS 7 timbers (Crone pers comm)
Chronologies from ships				
Z059m001	AD1371	AD1659	10.48	Klim Strandvraget 2 timbers (Daly 2011a)
Z071m001	AD1366	AD1594	8.73	Oslo Barcode ship 08 3 timbers (Daly 2011c)
Z157M001	AD1365	AD1565	8.51	Bispevika 12 ship Oslo 5 timbers (Daly & Daly 2016)
Z253M001	AD1339	AD1566	8.48	Bispevika 18 Oslo 2 timbers (Daly 2019a)
Z062m001	AD1384	AD1512	8.23	Oslo Vaterland I Schweigaardsgt 8 5 timbers (Daly 2011b)
SNorway ships	AD1304	AD1895	7.74	South Norway ships 63 timbers (Daly unpubl)
Z096M002	AD1351	AD1517	7.58	Bispevika 2 Oslo 3 timbers (Daly 2013)
WSshipsM01	AD1352	AD1636	7.21	West Swedish ships 29 timbers (Daly unpubl)
Z263M001	AD1356	AD1551	6.58	Bispevika 23 4 timbers (Daly 2019b)
Z141M001	AD1352	AD1539	6.35	Klippan 2 shipwreck Göteborg 11 timbers (Daly 2015)

Table 2. Femern vestlig landvinding wreck, Denmark. Result of the correlation between the average from the dated oaks from the ship construction (Z280M001) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Filenames	-	-	Z2801019 x26	
-	start	dates	AD1493	
-	dates	end	AD1617	
Master chronologies				
SM000005	AD1274	AD1974	4.01	Skåne Blekinge (Lund University)
Chronologies from ships				
Z043M001	AD1320	AD1577	6.04	Germany FPL 77 4AM wreck 5 timbers (Daly 2009)
Z239005a	AD1441	AD1581	5.01	Tunnelvraget Karlskrona 103 p5 bord garnering (Daly 2018b)
BAT6047a	AD1426	AD1586	4.59	Batavia Western Australia 6047 frame (Daly 2016c)
Z0923M01	AD1404	AD1623	4.54	Vasa group 1 63 timbers (Daly in press)
PP11201A	AD1490	AD1562	4.27	PL Gdansk-Lipce (Wazny pers comm)
baua2191	AD1534	AD1636	4.25	Ventjager (van Daalen & van der Beek 2003)
BTV0M001	AD1342	AD1616	4.11	Batavia Baltic 3 group 19 timbers (Daly & Domínguez Delmas 2017)
Z027M002	AD1313	AD1567	4.05	Amager Strand ship 9 timbers (Daly 2008)

Table 3. Femern vestlig landvinding wreck, Denmark. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve from the barrel stave (Z2801019) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Methodology

Measuring and analysis of the material is carried out using the program 'DENDRO' (Tyers, 1997) and for the calculation of the t -value (' t -test') 'CROS' (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) is used. In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are used. To estimate the felling date of the trees used to make the ship and the barrel stave two sapwood statistics are applicable. For the ship timbers, a statistic for South Norway (c. 15 sapwood years (-8+6)) is used (Christensen & Havemann 1998). For the barrel stave a sapwood average of c. 10-25 sapwood rings is used. Several calculations of the average sapwood in oaks in different regions in Northern Europe have been published, and as the provenance of the oak tree for the stave tends towards southern Scandinavia, I have here chosen to use a combination of the estimate for Northern Germany (ca. 20 sapwood years (-5+10) (Hollstein 1980)) and for Southern Norway.

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Catalogue

Filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
Samples											
Z2800019	Femern vestlig landvinding VIR2916 x1 frame QUSP	90			C	H/S?	N	S	N	1.38	undated
Z280002a	Femern vestlig landvinding VIR2929 x11 køl? QUSP	122	AD1443	AD1564	G	0	N	O	H1	1.14	after AD1572
Z2800039	Femern vestlig landvinding VIR2929 x9 spant QUSP	179	AD1362	AD1540	C	0	N	T	H1	0.88	after AD1548
Z280004a	Femern vestlig landvinding VIR2929 x8 planke QUSP	114	AD1408	AD1521	G	0	N	T	H1	0.97	after AD1529
Z2801019	Femern vestlig landvinding VIR2929 x26 barrel stave QUSP	125	AD1493	AD1617	G	0	N	R	H1	0.87	after AD1628
	Femern vestlig landvinding VIR2929 x10 QUSP	Not measured, too perforated with shipworm									
Averages											
Z280M001	Femern vestlig landvinding VIR2929 3 timbers QUSP	203	AD1362	AD1564						0.95	
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings. QUSP = <i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak. PISY = <i>Pinus sp.</i> , pine. PCAB = <i>Picea sp/Larix sp.</i> , spruce/larch. ABAL = <i>Abies sp.</i> , fir.											
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